

All at Sea: Addressing Information Anxiety in students embarking on research at third level

“Mistakes are the portals of discovery.” James Joyce.

Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to gain understanding of how negative affective factors such as confusion, doubt and shame students’ impact students’ ability to engage with research when they begin learning at third level so that faculty and academic libraries can better plan information literacy instruction and student outreach.

Approach – This paper analyses the literature on the role affective needs play in student interaction with information at third level, including insight on students helping-seeking behaviours and will examine the role of metacognition in information literacy, giving students greater insight to their affective needs so that they can approach information problems more effectively.

Findings – Negative affective factors are part of the experience of student research particularly in the initial stages of research before a focus is formulated. These affective factors often remain hidden and inhibit students’ willingness to seek help and even jeopardise their decision to continue with study at third level. Students adhere to pre-existing methods of finding information with habit formation taking place in a student’s first year at college making this a watershed moment for information literacy intervention. This paper highlights the importance of developing critical thinking dispositions as part of the life-learning remit of information literacy of development.

Practical Applications – First year information literacy typically consists of one-off sessions with librarians as well as embedded instruction from faculty, assessment of which is part of the overall summative evaluation of student assignments. This paper explores how formative information literacy assessment such as reflective journals enhance a student’s metacognitive abilities enabling them to engage more independently and effectively with information. Insight into the affective factors preventing students from seeking help also aids the academic library in developing more innovative and effective methods of student outreach.

Originality –As fewer students approach librarians for assistance with queries and with more learning taking place remotely, this essay examines how libraries can anticipate the affective factors students experience when developing appropriate information literacy strategies.

Introduction:

This paper will examine the affective needs of incoming first year students when undertaking research, focusing on the phenomenon of information anxiety and suggest strategies which the academic library might employ in addressing these affective dimensions both in Information Literacy instruction and the reference encounter, empowering students to approach information use more confidently and effectively. With students due to begin their third level education in either a remote or blended learning environment this autumn, the uncertainty and isolated nature of this return and what Cathy Davidson calls the “emotional workload” (Davidson 2020) currently facing students, emphasises the unique affective environment facing this year’s first year undergraduates and calls for an increased awareness of how students entering college cope with the adjustment to more independent learning, including the help-seeking strategies they adopt when things do not go to plan.

Information Anxiety – background and theory

Mellon (1986) proposed a grounded theory of library anxiety that when undergraduates are faced with a research task in the library, they become so overwhelmed that they could not approach the task “logically or effectively” (p.279). Though affective barriers in the library experience of undergraduate students have been an area of much research for decades, the advent of the internet and in particular Web 2.0 technology has shifted the focus from libraries as a source of anxiety to include the affective factors relating to this ubiquity of information online on student research (Blundell & Lambert 2013; Naveed 2020). The information landscape of the digital age is vast, expansive, and unknown with users at risk of drowning in a sea of data. An issue facing today’s students compared to those of a previous generation is the overwhelm created by the sheer vastness of information sources unlike previous generations who struggled with scarcity of resources (Head, PIL, *What Can Be Learned* 2013). In Mellon’s research on library anxiety, students described feeling lost due to the labyrinthine maze of the library itself; Kuhlthau (1991) argued that understanding information use has traditionally centred on information systems or the bibliographic paradigm, placing emphasis on order and certainty, whereas understanding information use from the user perspective emphasises the uncertainty and confusion typically experienced by users particularly when embarking on information search.

Wurman argued in *Information Anxiety* (1991), first published in 1989, that anxiety is created by the “ever widening gap between what we understand and what we think we should

understand. Information anxiety is the black hole between data and knowledge, and it happens when information doesn't tell us what we want or need to know." (p.34) Wurman argued that the "information explosion" negatively impacted people's ability to engage with learning. Wurman's text was published at the inception of the World Wide Web and decades before the ubiquity of Smartphones, anticipating a further "information explosion" created by the digital age, highlighting the acceleration of change in this area and raising questions about how these interim decades have further impacted affective needs when gathering formation. Wurman (1991) outlines five rings of information, in terms of their direct relevance to our lives, with the first ring "internal information" being the cerebral messages regulating our bodies, and the information level "We have perhaps the least control over[...] but are most affected by" (p.43). The other rings, according to Wurman, encompass conversational information, reference information, news information and cultural information. Wurman contends that anxiety can occur at any of these levels which "can paralyze thinking and prevent learning" (p.44).

Wurman's (1991) central argument in *Information Anxiety* is that anxiety stems from people's access to information being inhibited which, as he explains, occurs in a number of ways: "not understanding information; feeling overwhelmed by the amount of information to be understood; not knowing if certain information exists; not knowing where to find information; and perhaps the most frustrating, knowing exactly where to find the information but not key to access it" (p.44). For example, students interested in following the citation trail of an online blog or article may encounter barriers such as broken URLs or lack of awareness of paywalls preventing certain research being accessible, features which frustrate the process of research and discourage the student from delving deeper. Though Wurman (1991) prescribes access as the key antidote to anxiety, adding however that access should not be confused with efficiency and order, a focus on the quickest way of retrieving information which ignores how information is often gathered tangentially, through conversation, chance and segue and that these components are often key in gaining understanding. Wurman (1991) deems the "understanding business" as the key element in the triumvirate of information dissemination (the other two being transmission and storage) and is the "bridge between data and knowledge" (p.45)

Naveed and Anwar (2020) revisited Wurman's conceptualisation of information anxiety and proposed a new framework to go beyond what they deem to be its limited scope, due in some part to its inception when the web was still in its infancy. Their criticism of

Wurman's framework is that it addresses information use up to the point of access only, with their model (2020) going beyond it to incorporate six dimensions of information use including "task conceptualisation, need recognition, finding information, evaluating information, accessing information and using information" (p.69), where anxiety may arise at any individual stage or from a combination of these stages. The authors outline that the model is not linear but "encourages a variety of alternative strategies such as jumping around, branching off, or looping back" (p.70). Understanding this is important for the information professional to assist students and for students to gain insight into their own experience. Both task conceptualisation and need recognition are particularly relevant to first year students and align with the pre-focus stage of information use, considered most problematic for students (Head 2013; Kuhlthau 1991; Kennedy et al 1999). However, even students adept at one or more stages, for example conceptualising task and finding information, may struggle at others, for example the access stage, due to a lack of insight on issues such as copyright or paywall restrictions, with Naveed and Anwar (2020) acknowledging the negative feelings of frustration and stress this brings at the end of intensive searching.

Transition from learning at secondary to third level in the Digital Age

Though Wurman underlines the importance of discovery in learning, many of the strategies which undergraduate students employ when searching for information are based on "efficiency and predictability" (Head, *What Can Be Learned* 2013 p.472) according to studies undertaken from 2008 to 2013 by Project Information Literacy. Head (2013) argues that students are often ill-equipped when entering university to deal with the complexity of research at third level and proficiency at attaining declarative information quickly belies a lack of evaluative skills for deeper learning and that many students persist in their choice of search tools "driven by familiarity and habit" (*Learning the Ropes*, p.29). Head (2013) identifies first year as a critical year in the development of good research skills, as after this time, students are in danger of "flatlining" (*Learning the Ropes* p.30). Most students surveyed by Project Information Literacy since 2008 have identified the beginning of search to be the most challenging and the stage with most negatively associated emotions, some of which are

illustrated in an infographic summarising their key findings (Figure 1).

Fig. 1

Many students' go-to for beginning research when entering third level, based on studies undertaken by Project Information Literacy between 2008 - 2013, was Google (Head,

2013, *Learning the Ropes*). However many students soon discovered this to be an unsatisfactory strategy when it came to fulfilling requirements of college-level assignments acknowledging the need to go beyond this strategy but also a fear of becoming “mired in the weeds of research” (*Learning the Ropes*, p.3) This feeling of overwhelm at the prospect of college research is also evidenced in a study of first year’s attitudes to research through reflective journals (McGuinness and Breen 2007) , with one student writing about their loss of motivation due to the “long hours which lie ahead clawing through irrelevant information” (p.34). Other reasons which students gave as reasons for feelings of overwhelm from this study included the number of irrelevant sources produced during searches., getting side-tracked from their topic as well as overwhelm at the amount of information available and devising effective search strategies (McGuinness and Brien’s, 2007). Some students persist with using Google regardless of their transition to third level study (*What Can Be Learned* Head 2013). Rowland et al. (2008) point to the danger of assuming that students who grew up with Google resultingly possess the skills necessary for research in college, arguing that literature from the previous 25 years does not indicate an improvement in students’ information skills but in some cases a decline; and insists on the need for students to understand the information landscape to navigate it successfully. Daland (2015) comments that though many libraries are migrating to more intuitive discovery systems, students still require an awareness of search- term formulations, unlike the whole-sentence approach of Google, as well as an ability to critically evaluate sources.

Breivik (1998) critiques the research paper as a form of assessment for undergraduates as she argues it can lead to students missing out on the broader context of a topic, allowing students to succeed once they “pull together just enough ‘at random’ information to support the requirements of the paper” (p.35) and that technology has enabled a surface approach to information gathering, where instead of honing their searching skills, “Most students are content with whatever materialises from their first few keystrokes” (p.35). This concern is echoed by Barbara Fisher (2012) who also questions the research paper as a way of developing students research practices where they learn to make informed choice of sources, suggesting that instead the format encourages choices made on convenience and panic where students “grab articles from which they can easily mine some quotes, often pulling some out-of-context lines from the first page without reading further” (<https://www.projectinfolit.org/>). However, the perennial nature of this difficult transition to third level research is illustrated by Edwards in a 1927 essay entitled “Why

Freshmen Fail”, where he argued the reason students struggle in this transitional phase is because they “have never learned to dig and dig and dig until the assigned task is completed” (p.120)

Eklof (2013) refers to the amount of distraction which students face whilst studying in the digital age, including texting, social media use, online browsing and listening to music on headphones all while engaging in research, questioning the impact which such multi-tasking holds for students’ ability to focus. Neuroscientist Dr Russell Poldrack (2011) shared his concerns with Project Information Literacy for the type of learning taking place when students are exposed to so many distractions and how this impacts the deep learning necessary to focus on one source. The type of deep learning he refers to relies on memory formation, something which is inhibited when the mind’s attention is split on different tasks. Furthermore, he questions how this threat to student’s ability to focus on a topic or source might be compounded by the cognitive deterioration associated with age. However, Davidson (2014) contends that multi-tasking is in fact the ideal mode for students of the digital age, arguing that students have developed new ways of reading to cope with these new formats. Davidson (2011) refers to the term in neuroscience called “attention blindness” which describes the way our brains filter extraneous activity when it is solely focused on a specific task. Davidson (2011) sees the possibilities this holds for learning through collaboration as by doing so we can each compensate for individual blind spots (Chronicle of Higher Education). This “collaboration by difference” includes discussions between Davidson’s students about “how accident, disruption, distraction and difference increase the motivation to learn and to solve problems, both individually and collectively” and is illustrative of a more reflective and dynamic style of learning which acknowledges that missteps, diversions and chance are an intrinsic part of learning and to be embraced rather than avoided (Davidson, Chronicle of Higher Education 2011).

Psychological and Affective Dimensions in the Information Search Process of students beginning research at third level

Kuhlthau (1991) emphasised the centrality of affective states on the Information Search Process as learning itself is a process which involves the whole person (cognition, feelings and actions) and that affective states can determine whether a person proceeds in their information task, if the new information proves too unsettling or challenging to a person’s world view. Kuhlthau (1991) identified six stages in the ISP and the likely affective

experience of each stage. Uncertainty dominates at the beginning stage, followed by optimism in the second ‘selection’ stage and then by confusion, doubt, and frustration in the third stage before a topic is settled on. Kuhlthau (1991) based her study of the information search process on George Kelly’s (1963) personal construct theory where a person derives meaning from the information they encounter through their emotional responses or personal constructs in processing that information. Kelly (1963) argued that new information can threaten the constructs a person already holds, leading to doubt and confusion at this early stage of information use and that the person reaches a turning point once they formulate a new hypothesis incorporating this new information into their existing constructs. Kennedy et al. (1999) argue against directing students to find a focus too early in the search process and outline how strategies advised by information professionals to avoid overload and achieve efficiency in the pre-focus stage of search are counterproductive and provide a false sense of focus before students are exposed to the breadth of information sources available. This initial stage, where students “engage in explorative, undefined, or unfocused information-seeking behaviour” (Kennedy et al. 1999, p.268), necessitates a certain amount of overwhelm, doubt and confusion when students are faced with the vastness of resources available, but is necessary in helping to provide the student with awareness of key contextual information of a topic before narrowing their focus. Nahl (2004) underlines the centrality of feelings and motivation to all information search and without these “affective filters”, information lacks value to the individual, leading some to relinquish their search altogether in favour of some other activity. Based on a study by Carver & Scheier (2001) who observed a correlation between positive affective states and greater flexibility in user search strategies, Nahl’s study examined the correlation between affective load and user coping skills, concluding that uncertainty contributes to the affective load of users with inadequate coping skills.

Heinström (2005) studied the impact of psychological factors, namely personality (based on the Five Factor Model of Personality by Costa and McCrae, 1992) and approaches to study on how students search for information and showed that these factors had a stronger influence on information seeking than other factors such as field of study or stage of thesis development. According to Heinström’s study (2005), those with a tendency for fast surfing of information (i.e. on search engines) rated lower on both the conscientious and ‘openness to new experiences’ scales of the personality test and sought information which confirmed their existing perceptions. In this study fast surfing correlates with negative affective states, where students impacted by external factors do not delve behind this level of information search and

often experience difficulties at a later stage due to a lack of critical engagement with the information. Those who displayed broad scanning behaviour typically scored higher than average on the extraversion, competitiveness, and 'openness to new ideas' scales, typically displaying strong critical thinking skills. Those who showed 'deep diving' behaviour displayed a more systematic approach to study as well as strong critical thinking skills; but unlike broad scanners seldom came upon information by chance (Heinström, 2005).

Understanding Help Seeking Behaviour of Undergraduate Students

Information anxiety as a situational anxiety is heightened by feelings of isolation and a reluctance to articulate the problem with others (Blecher-Cohen 2019). Research from Project Information Literacy indicates that 80 percent of students do not approach librarians for help (Figure 2), while many studies have been carried out on the role affective factors play in the reluctance of students to consult library staff. Mellon (1986) identified that students experiencing library anxiety avoid approaching library staff for help because of feelings of shame around exposing their perceived inadequacy. However, Bailey's (1997) study found that students avoided asking librarians for help predominantly because they perceived that librarians could not help them. McAfee (2018) writes of the difficulty of effectively measuring emotional factors and underlines the hidden nature of affective factors meaning they often remain concealed from quantitative and qualitative studies of student attitudes to libraries. McAfee (2018) acknowledges the significance of Mellon specifying shame, as opposed to fear, as the basis for library anxiety as well as identifying shame's recursive nature, which entraps the sufferer, paralysing them from taking action. Shame is viewed as a socially regulating emotion (Gilbert 1998) linked to a person's success at completing a task (Piers and Singer 1971) and when Jiao & Onwuegbuzie (2002) studied the social interdependence aspect of library anxiety, they discovered that students with elevated levels of socially prescribed perfectionism also displayed elevated levels of library anxiety. Jiao & Onwuegbuzie (2002) did not find a correlation between students with anxiety disorders and library anxiety, but they found that traits such as perfectionism and procrastination did correlate with elevated levels of library anxiety, which as McAfee (2018) states are viewed by psychoanalysts as ways of avoiding negative self-evaluation. Many studies point to how students seek help with information search via informal channels such as peer support (Naveed 2017; Bailey 1997; Head 2013) with Gross & Latham (2007) highlighting this as problematic given students' lack of insight on their personal proficiency

in information literacy, based on their study which showed an inverse correlation between skill attainment in information literacy and student estimation of it.

Fig. 2

The information literate student was described in the American Library Association's Presidential Committee on Information Literacy report (1989) as one who has "learned how to learn" (<http://www.ala.org>) and is therefore prepared to continue self-directed learning beyond college. Most recently, the Chartered Institute of Information and Library Professionals (CILIP) (2018) provided an updated definition of information literacy to underline the significance of critical thinking in information literacy:

Information literacy is the ability to think critically and make balanced judgements about any information we find and use. It empowers us as citizens to develop informed views and to engage fully with society. (<https://infolit.org.uk/>)

Naveed and Anwar (2020) argue that information anxiety occurs when users are ill equipped to navigate the increasing amount of information available and that information literacy empowers users to use information confidently rather than anxiously. However, information literacy has been described as an area beset with "semantic disagreements" (McGuinness & Brien 2007, p.23); with Bawden (2009) dismissing the information literacy movement as a "solution in search of a problem" (p.181), arguing that its "library-centric" and linear models ignore the dynamic nature of information use in the Web 2.0 universe, as well as ignoring the personal dimension of engagement with information. The omission of subjectivity in information literacy in many of the standards and rubrics of information literacy has been a key point of contention and created difficulties with how information literacy is measured in students (McGuinness & Brien 2007). The subjective aspect of information literacy development was examined by McGuinness and Brien (2007) who used reflective journals as formative assessment to gain insight on the student perspective of the research process of first year undergraduates enrolled in an information literacy module. This demonstrates Kulthau's (1994) objective of process intervention where students gain insight on their research practices through writing about them and unlike note-taking, journal writing gives students the freedom and creativity to make connections amongst the information they encounter as well as the perspective to identify gaps in their information search. Journaling promotes honest and personal appraisal of the research process allowing students to develop their metacognitive capabilities and "recognise and harness the different emotive and affective stages" (p.28) of their learning experience, allowing students to attain autonomy and confidence in their own ability to approach learning tasks. As Fourie and Van Niekert (1999) point out, traditional assessment methods such as term papers often portray the student experience of learning as being a seamless one, with formative assessment tools such as

reflective journals allowing students to reflect on the difficulties (as well as positive factors) of learning and work out their own ways of overcoming these factors the next time, giving students a sense of power over the learning process. It also means that students confront issues honestly about their process of finding information – for example admitting they do not know where to find quality journal articles and explore ideas around how they might find such, rather than resorting to last-minute shortcuts in their information search such as quick Google searching to find a quote to satisfy the assignment brief to hand.

Critical Thinking Dispositions in Information Literacy

Mellon's research on library anxiety showed the impact negative affective states had on students' ability to approach library search "logically or effectively" (p.279). Onwuegbuzie, Jiao and Bostick (2004) elaborated on this insight by proposing that library anxiety created negative thinking disposition which had a harmful impact on students' ability to focus on their task and subsequently impacted their academic performance and ability to engage with their course work. Kwon et al. (2007) present a study of the relationship between critical thinking dispositions and library anxiety highlighting the symbiotic nature of affect and cognition in influencing how students learn. Thinking dispositions relate to the intellectual tendencies a person displays under a given set of conditions (Kwon et al. p. 270) and for this study included dimensions such as "truth-seeking", "open-mindedness" and "analyticity". Kwon et al. (2007) assess the dispositions of those with strong critical thinking skills, based on a Delphi study, as a way of offering insight for instructional librarians in planning more effective programmes so that students learn to recognise that "cognitive uncertainty and emotional ups and downs" (p.276) are to be expected during the research process.

Information Literacy as a Metaliteracy

The seismic changes in the information landscape since the 1989 ACRL report, including the increasingly porous boundaries between those who contribute to information and those who seek it on digital channels, such as social media platforms and online communities, have led to increased attention as to what constitutes information literacy. Commentators such as Christine Pawley have noted the contradictions inherent in the notion of information literacy, given its opposing ideals of citizen empowerment through wider access to information, alongside a concern over controlling the quality of the information accessed (p.67); and argues that a critical rather than a skills approach is needed in

information literacy. Mackey & Jacobson (2011) argue that the dynamic information environment of the digital age, where users are also potential contributors of information, requires a reframing of information literacy as a metaliteracy to “promote critical thinking and collaboration in a digital age” (p.62) which “provides the higher order thinking required to engage with multiple document types through various media formats in collaborative environments” (p.70) As a metaliteracy, students are equipped to deal with the ever-evolving information formats of the digital age, rather than the paper-bound origins of traditional IL, or the medium specific literacies such as digital literacy or cyber literacies, enabling users to adapt these critical literacy skills to new technologies in an evolving information landscape. Users must develop “a critical thinking filter” (Mackey & Jacobson 2011 p. 72) when engaging on any of the multitude of information systems, such as Twitter and Facebook whose use of push technology means that information is brought to the user, in order to distinguish information of value, or as Wurman (1991) would describe it, attempting to traverse “the black hole between data and knowledge” (p.34). Another issue encountered by the user of Web 2.0 is the decontextualization and fragmentation of information making provenance of work complicated where part of a text appears outside of its original holder (Mackey and Jacobson 2011). Mackey and Jacobson (2011) question the suitability of federated search where the certainty of results often “lulls information seekers into a false sense of security” regardless of the value of those results to the user. (p.71).

The American College and Research Library Framework 2015

The ACRL Framework (2015) recognises the “dynamic and uncertain information ecosystem” of the Web 2.0 universe stating that “Students have a greater role and responsibility in creating new knowledge, in understanding the contours and the changing dynamics of the world of information, and in using information, data, and scholarship ethically” (p.7). Rather than a set of skills or competency standards, the 2015 Framework outlines six interconnected threshold concepts, as well as associated knowledge practices and dispositions to help libraries and other institutions assist students in responding to the evolving information landscape. The Framework (2015) is guided by the concept of metaliteracy as outlined by Mackey and Jacobson and which it states “demands behavioural, affective, cognitive and metacognitive engagement with the information ecosystem” (p.8) The Framework focuses particularly on metacognition, which as Livingston (1997;2003) explained is an awareness of one’s own learning processes, development of which comes

through critical self- reflection, and places this personal relationship with information use as central to its definition of information literacy:

Information literacy is the set of integrated abilities encompassing the reflective discovery of information, the understanding of how information is produced and valued, and the use of information in creating new knowledge and participating ethically in communities of learning. (ACRL Framework 2015, p.8)

Challenges facing the academic library in implementing effective information literacy programmes:

Daland (2015) identifies a rise in student intake and an ever-expanding information ecology with a stagnancy in library staff numbers, which places an emphasis on effective and efficient library instruction which equips students to become more self-sufficient learners. However, many library instruction courses suffer from a lack of perceived relevance, where students may not see the need for them, living as they do in the digital age, with undergraduate students, struggling to come to terms with their new course of study, often dismissive of library instruction's relevance to their needs. Gross and Latham (2007) point to those with a lower skill level in IL are more likely to overestimate their capabilities and less likely to realise their need for instruction. Lierman and Santiago (2019) cite the growing emphasis on remote learning as an issue facing academic libraries in continuing to provide high quality IL instruction.

The Significance of Context and Timing in Information Literacy Intervention

Kuhlthau (1994) outlines the necessity for a shift in the role of librarian in the information age from one who provides source intervention to that of process intervention, namely as a counsellor, through advantageously timed interventions. Kuhlthau (1994) identified five stages or zones of intervention based on Vygotsky's (1978) concept of "zones of proximal development", where a student's own problem-solving abilities are enhanced through guidance from knowledgeable peers or professionals. The ZPD has been identified as a motivational space where students gain insight on how to manage anxiety or frustration on the learning task through engagement with others (Walker, R. A. 2010, p.713). This provides a diagnostic model of intervention in assisting students who approach the reference desk and an acceptance of what Kuhlthau deems the "uncertainty principle" (p.63), where information professionals diagnose the student's stage of information need as well as identifying whether it is a product (source) problem or a process problem. Information professionals then base

their intervention based on the corresponding stage with the first four stages requiring a product or source intervention and with students in stage five requiring a process intervention. Kuhlthau (1994) outlines the ways in which librarians might intervene as counsellor to students in the information process:

- collaboration (either with peers or partnering with librarian) to lessen the isolation of individual research;
- continuation, acknowledging that information search evolves;
- conversation – to encourage students to discuss their ideas;
- charting – to help students visually present large amounts of information
- composing – this might include encouraging the student to write a reflective journal

Breen and Fallon (2005) argue that librarians and faculty can help students to negotiate the challenges of the contemporary information environment through “creating the appropriate learning opportunities and contexts” (p.179) to develop the student’s skills for lifelong learning, given the range and complexity of information sources available. Breen and Fallon posit that an embedded approach in the curriculum is more effective in attaining literacy to any standalone instructions, where students encounter numerous situations where they must exercise their information skills throughout their programme of study. One-shot library instruction is deemed ineffective due to a lack of student motivation and the risk of overwhelming students with too much information on sources. The authors identify two learning situations where information literacy ideally occurs – project and problem-based learning situations. These situations critically provide a context for student engagement in the information task but must be supported by adequate direction to appropriate sources or students will continue to use the sources they are familiar with.

Daland (2015) examines the timing of information literacy instruction on student motivation, based on Kuhlthau’s prognosis that the best time to intervene with students is during the fourth stage of information searching, problem formulation, and surveys two groups of students for outcomes, with one group writing their final year thesis and the second group at various stages of a bachelor’s degree, based on the “success method” of search by Zins (2000). Zins’ ‘success method’ helps students improve their search strategy through following five steps of 5 W’s:

- What (what is their research question for their assignment?)

- Where (where should they look for information?)
- Words (find keywords from their problem along with synonyms)
- Work (actually doing their search)
- Wow (evaluating their search result). (summarised in Daland 2015, p. 131)

Zins' method (2000) includes reflection on student experience of search and its outcomes and as Daland comments allows the instruction librarian to shift the focus of library instruction away from "mechanical search interface demonstrations" (p.131) to equipping the student with a systematic search process. This emphasis on process intervention means that librarians can move from the identifier to the counsellor role as outlined by Kuhlthau. Both groups in Daland's (2015) study found the instruction helpful, particularly the "source criticism" section, suggesting this is the area students of the Google generation struggle with most. The study found that the group who received instruction during an assignment rated the library search engine over Google, whereas the second group ranked Google over library search, suggesting that library instruction is optimally given when students are tasked with a specific information problem such as an assignment (Daland 2015).

Going Online: Metaliteracy and ACRL Framework as part of Asynchronous IL Instruction at the University of Houston

To meet the needs of increased online learning and the subsequent demand this creates for instructional library teams, whilst adhering to the high educational standards achieved through in-person instruction, the University of Houston designed an asynchronous information literacy programme incorporating the 2015 Framework. Pedagogically, Lierman and Santiago (2019) are strongly guided by Ramsden's view of deep learning which they state is characterised by "active learning experiences, personal relevance for students, clear expectations, and opportunities for choice" (p.208). As part of the deep learning remit of the course, each section is guided by knowledge practices from the ACRL Framework and includes space for reflection in assessment. Students complete tasks linked to real-world assignments such as mind mapping in the research question section. Though designed so that students can individually work at their own pace, the software allows for students' reflective work to be saved so that feedback can be provided by faculty and librarians and used in collaborative group settings to enable peer learning, a feature which the authors point out helps to mitigate the isolated nature of asynchronous learning, providing an opportunity for Davidson's idea of "collaboration by difference".

The reference interview as an opportunity for “small teaching” with big impact

Wurman (1991) advised that communication “equals remembering what it’s like not to know” (p.130). The reference interview, when carried out in consideration of the student’s point of view, provide opportunities for “small teaching” (Lang 2016) which in turn can lead to significant changes in a student’s approach to research and the academic library. However, Eklof (2013) links the demise in students accessing the reference interview with increasing numbers of students more likely to seek help online as this avoids the personal aspect of asking someone for help, citing Brown (2011) who contends that though numbers approaching the desk are dwindling, its significance has not. Eklof (2013) advises that when a student approaches the reference desk, it is usually their last port of call and they have probably “exhausted all other options” (p.256) and that library staff should focus on establishing a “bridge of communication” with the student, where they pay as much attention to listening to the student as to dispensing advice, allowing for the difficulty students experience in articulating their true information need. Blecher-Cohen (2019) also underlines the value of developing a more collaborative approach in the reference interview and suggests “linguistic matching” (Stock 2009) with the student either in person or virtually to achieve enhanced engagement, which may go some way to help dismantle some of the perceived barriers of approaching academic library staff. Eklof (2013) advises that the librarian desist from further adding to information overload by ensuring they clearly explain the steps taken in addressing the information need. The reference interview provides an opportunity for the reference librarian to suggest other interesting databases to explore and the potential to create a positive learning experience where the patron feels comfortable at returning (Eklof 2013).

Despite the reference interview’s significance in enhancing student engagement with information, Blecher-Cohen (2019) warns that if academic libraries wait for students to come to them “they have already failed” (p.359), stating that those most in need of their services have either “too much anxiety or too little motivation” (p.363) to approach the reference desk. Blecher-Cohen (2019) outlines how libraries need to reimagine more flexible ways of providing outreach to best meet the needs of their students and suggests bringing opportunities for reference to the classrooms, where postgraduate students trained in information literacy and research skills are embedded within departments to provide a point of need liaison to students. Benefits to having this liaison role embedded in the department help to diminish barriers students perceive with library staff, meaning that students may be

more likely to seek help and the increased availability of students and their familiarity with assignment expectations make them ideally suited to this position (Blecher-Cohen 2019). According to Blecher-Cohen (2019), libraries need to present their information literacy programmes in a way that underlines its relevance to students, so that instead of marketing information literacy classes as a way of doing research properly, libraries need to recognise students' existing competencies in research and market information literacy education as of helping students to achieve better results with less hassle.

In dealing with the overwhelming nature of information available, Hartog (2017) advises teaching students effective reading strategies which adapt their information need both to the time available and the student's existing knowledge level of a subject and suggests directing students to formats such as podcasts, audiobooks and Twitter feeds which may provide more digestible versions of information than articles or books. For example, students who are at the beginning stages of research may benefit from gaining some helpful contextual knowledge to a subject by listening to podcasts, helping to expand student horizons beyond the go-to background source of Wikipedia (consulted by 82% of students in the early stages of research – PIL 2013) and reflects Wurman's (1991) concept of how in order for learning to take place "it must stimulate your curiosity in some way" (p.138) and that providing accessible routes into major concepts are the key to diminishing anxiety about information.

Conclusion:

Wurman describes education as essentially "nurturing an interest" (p.154) and learning as "the process of remembering what you are interested in" (p.138); arguing that guilt and anxiety paralyse learning by preventing the nurturing of interest and the subsequent "movement of information into memory" (p154). Though Web 2.0 has expanded access to information, this places greater emphasis on improving people's ability to critically engage with information. Academic libraries can meet some of these challenges by enhancing their outreach, by bringing opportunities for reference to the classroom and conveying the message of information literacy as something which helps rather than hinders students in their research (Blecher-Cohen 2019). Acknowledging the challenges inherent in learning (as well as the joys) and developing a more reflective approach to information literacy empowers students to gain insight into their metacognitive processes, enabling them to develop critical thinking skills that stand them in good stead over a lifetime of learning and discovery.

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